

***From Waste to Value: Creating
Composite Blends out of Waste Low-
Density Polyethylene and Polystyrene
for Fused Deposition Modeling
Printing***

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Introduction, Goals & Objectives

Global Plastic Production and future trends

- Since the mid-20th century, global plastic production has increased exponentially.
- More than **500 million metric tons** of plastic were produced in **2024**.
- Forecasted to **34 billion tons** by **2050**
- **Single-use** packaging consumes nearly **40-50%** of all plastic produced, driving the industry's **unsustainable expansion**.

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Plastic Waste Crisis

- Approximately 400 million metric tons of plastic waste are produced annually, and **less than 10% is being recycled.**
- About 11 million metric tonnes are dumped in ocean. 2000 garbage trucks full of plastic everyday.
- Pollutes water, air, and soil, posing widespread risks with long-term **environmental challenges.**
- Discarded single-use plastics waste economic value and burden communities with cleanup costs.

Rethinking Plastic Waste for a Sustainable Future

- National regulations, corporate commitments, and innovative solutions are essential to reducing plastic waste, improving recyclability, and enhancing waste management infrastructure.

LDPE: Bridging the Gap Between Production and Sustainability

- PE is the most common commodity plastic → around 1/3 of the global plastic production.
- More than **35 Million Metric Tons** of LDPE waste produced in 2024, and **only 5% of LDPE production is recycled annually**:
 - ✘ Challenging to process
 - ✘ Inferior mechanical properties
 - ✘ Property degradation issues
- **Need:** To improve plastic waste recycling via Additive Manufacturing (AM), and it is important to understand how variations in the Melt Flow Index (MFI) of LDPE affect printability and material performance. This knowledge can support better material selection and improve consistency in recycled products.

From Waste to Resource: Recycling Pathway

Additive Manufacturing

Sorting, shredding, washing, drying, compounding, 3D printing

- ✓ Simple processes (with reduced waste)
- ✓ Suitable for large-scale
- ✓ Energy efficient
- ✗ Limited plastics
- ✗ Limited by material properties
- ✗ Limited by contaminations

Goals & Objectives

- ***Primary Objective:*** Boosting sustainability of various LDPE grades by systematically assessing the printability of LDPE/PS blends and relating their rheological and mechanical properties to printability through FDM. The study aims to offer practical strategies for converting waste LDPE into functional 3D printing filaments.

From Waste to Value: Creating Composite Blends out of Waste Low-Density Polyethylene and Polystyrene for Fused Deposition Modeling Printing

Materials: Unlocking the Value of Waste

LDPE:

(MFI: 8.0 g/10 min at 190 °C) LA
(MFI: 1.2 g/10 min at 190 °C) CW

Poor adhesion 50-100 mJ/m²
High shrinkage 2-3%
High Viscosity
Blending compatibility issues

Compatibilizer (SEBS copolymer):

Bonds with both polymers

Polystyrene:

Strong adhesion 300-400 mJ/m²
Low shrinkage 0.5-1%
Low viscosity
Non-spoolable (brittle)

Compatible

Materials: Unlocking the Value of Waste

Explored Parameters:

- ✓ Content of LDPE (Industrial waste)
- ✓ Content of LDPE (Consumer waste)
- ✓ Content of PS (Styrofoam waste)
- ✓ Content of copolymer (SEBS)

Sample Code: **X** **1** **2** **3** **4**

Blend Ratio (IW-PE) Blend Ratio (PS)
Compatibilizer Blend Ratio (CW-PE) Compatibilizer Dosage [%]

Materials: Transforming Waste Into Worth

Sample #	Sample Code	LA-LDPE[g]	CW-LDPE[g]	PS[g]	SEBS Copolymer[g]
1	CW-LDPE	-	10.0	-	-
2	LA-LDPE	10.0	-	-	-
3	PS	-	10	-	-
4	X-0550	-	5.0	5.0	-
5	X-0730	-	7.0	3.0	-
6	X-2250	2.5	2.5	5.0	-
7	X-3330	3.5	3.5	3.0	-
8	F-0554	-	5.0	5.0	0.4
9	F-0734	-	7.0	3.0	0.4
10	F-2254	2.5	2.5	5.0	0.4
11	F-3334	3.5	3.5	3.0	0.4

W/LA-LDPE – Waste/LA0710 Low Density Polyethylene

Methods: From Waste to Value

LDPE Bottles Shrink wrap
Cut into small pieces

Collected &
Washed

Stored

Shredded

Dried

Methods: From Waste to Value

Waste: LDPE & PS
Virgin: SEBS

GALOMB Mix-Molder

Thermal
 Mechanical
 Rheological
 Microstructure

Printability Assessment

- ✓ Degradation Temperature: Maximize
- ✓ E/η^* : Maximize (prevent buckling)
- ✓ ωc : maximize (this minimizes chain relaxation time)
- ✓ λ : Minimize
- ✓ Circularity: Maximize (prevent nozzle clogging)

Single-screw extruder
 (Filament maker)

3D printing
 Circularity Measurement

MATLAB

Methods: Sample Testing Protocol

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)

Tensile

Parallel Plate

Methods: Printability Testing

Tensile test

- Compare mechanical properties
- Validate material suitability
- Optimize printing temperature

Overhang

- Challenges mechanical stability
- Unsupported layers
- Tests material bonding
- Sensitive to material flow behavior

Thin-walled cube

- Layer adhesion
- Warpage tendencies
- Dimensional stability

Bridge

- Ability to span gaps
- Resistance to sagging = Tensile Strength
- Cooling Efficiency = Relaxation
- Warpage

Results: Thermal Characterization

DSC

- The melting temp of CW-LDPE was slightly higher than IW-LDPE
- Incorporating SEBS has **no significant effect on melting peak and the degree of crystallization.**

TGA

- Decomposition onset temperature for all blends was observed around $390 \pm 15 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
- **Thermal stability decreases** with increasing CW-LDPE content.

Results: Mechanical Characterization (Tensile)

Tensile Test

Results: Rheological Characterization (Parallel Plate)

- Increasing PS dosage

Enlarges the relaxation time

Increases E/η^*

- Incorporating IW-LDPE **reduces** λ

- Compatibilized blends with lowest λ (**relaxation time**)

F3334

Results: Rheological Characterization (Parallel Plate)

➤ A higher E/η^* ratio = Reduced buckling

F3334

➤ Circularity

81%

Results: Microstructural Characterization (SEM)

SEM

F3334 Molded

Results: Microstructural Characterization (SEM)

F3334 3D printed

Raster Angle

- Alternate 45°/45°
- Balanced strength
- Reduce anisotropy

Printing parameters

- 205°C
- 20 mm/s

det	WD	dwell	HV	pressure	mag	□	1 mm
ETD	25.8 mm	30 μs	15.00 kV	1.09e-3 Pa	100 x		F3334

Results: Mechanical Properties of 3D printed specimens

- Strength and Elastic Modulus of Molded Vs 3D Printed.
- Decreased by less than 20%.
- Highlights Printing induced defects and poor layer adhesion.

Results: Mechanical Properties of 3D printed specimens

- Significant decrease in strain at fracture for both the 3D printed blends
- Interlayer bonding weakness
- Porosity and voids as stress concentrators
- Rapid cooling during extrusion

Results: Overhang & Bridge

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Results: Cube

- Significant shrinkage at the bottom corners

due to:

- Sharp thermal gradient

- Extreme layer delamination

- Lack of heat retention leading to

- accelerated cooling

- Weakened layer adhesion

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Summary

- Consumer waste LDPE alone is highly unprintable due to its low MFI.
- Addition of Compatibilizer significantly improves mechanical properties
- Addition of High MFI IW LA-LDPE and PS to CW LDPE can improve the mechanical properties and make it effectively printable.
 - Interlayer delamination still stays.
- 3D printed specimens showed
 - Comparable Strength and reduced Elastic modulus (Compared to Molded specimens)
 - Highly printable bridges and overhangs
 - Extreme interlayer delamination was observed in cube due to lack of heat retention and high thermal gradient

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THANK YOU

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Interaction of PS and LDPE

Aspect	Polystyrene (PS)	Low-Density Polyethylene (LDPE)
Polarity	Non-polar, aromatic	Non-polar, aliphatic
Main Functional Group	Phenyl ring ($-C_6H_5$)	Saturated $-CH_2-CH_2-$ chains
Chain Rigidity	Rigid (due to benzene ring)	Flexible
Interacts with Styrene Blocks	Yes — π - π stacking of phenyl rings	No interaction
Interacts with Ethylene/Butylene Blocks	No effective interaction	Yes — Van der Waals & chain entanglement
Interacts with Maleic Anhydride (MA)	Poor — PS lacks reactive groups	Possible dipole-induced dipole or weak polar interactions with oxidized LDPE
Bonding Mechanisms	Physical: π - π stacking (with styrene), otherwise none	Physical: Chain entanglement, weak polar bonding (if oxidized)